

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE METHOD OF FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Akmal Aripjonovich Amanov

Namangan state Institute of foreign languages

mr_anderson.uz@mail.ru

ANNOTATION

This article discusses the role of intercultural communication in English language classes in higher education institutions and the advantages of effective methods and approaches in teaching it. We know that in the Educational Method, we understand the additional control mechanism for the organization and implementation of departments and programs to support certain provision measures by the teacher. Educational technique is a tool that reflects the success of the educational process and the competence of the teacher.

Keywords: *Teaching Methodology, Competency, Quality of Teaching, Effective Methods, Quality Education.*

OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODINI O'ZIGA XOS JIXATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tili darslarida madaniyatlararo muloqotni o'rni va uni o'qitishda samarali usul va yondashuvlarning afzalliklari muhokama qilinadi. Ta'lim usuli - bu o'qituvchi tomonidan ma'lum maqsadlarga erishish uchun bir qator ta'lim vositalari va

tadbirlarni tashkil etish va amalga oshirish uchun qo'llaniladigan mexanizm sanaladi. Shu bilan bir qatorda ta'lim texnikasi o'quv jarayonining muvaffaqiyati va o'qituvchining malakasini aks ettiruvchi vositadir.

***Kalit so'zlar:** O'qitish metodikasi, kompetentsiya, o'qitish sifati, samarali usullar, sifatli ta'lim.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching methods and approaches to language learning are great importance not only in primary education, but also in the higher education system. Communicative approaches to teaching English can too easily marginalize or ignore culture and intercultural perspectives, assuming (implicitly or explicitly) that learners aspire to a goal of something approaching idealized English native speaker competence. More than ever, this is a problematic assumption; the linguistic landscape for English is rapidly evolving as English becomes a global lingua franca for interaction between people from different first language backgrounds. The most useful teaching methods and techniques are those who have proven track record of success in employ the maximum number of the above criteria's, while each of them engages students in different ways, each has its benefits depending on the information they teach. Knowing the differences between these methods will help to select the technique that is best for particular class of study, and to define a particular teaching style.[1:186] The following characteristics of the most common teaching methods, as described in many related literatures, beside the above model will certainly help in choosing the right teaching and learning method. In teaching, it is true; we have to do with the student's body as well as with the mind. Our present purpose forbids extended reference to physiology, with which we must therefore assume that the reader is familiar. Pedagogics, however, consists so largely of psychology, and teachers are so generally in need of a compact restatement of the fundamental truths of psychology, that a chapter on this subject is indispensable in a treatise on pedagogics. The teacher of pedagogics should, accordingly, assure himself that his

students understand. The Method of Psychology, Mental Activity, and the Laws of Mental Activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, knowledge of a foreign language is of great importance, so it is necessary to reform the foreign language teaching system, to apply advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogic and information and communication technologies, and methods of increasing intercultural communication has become one of the most pressing issues in the world. Teaching English through interactive methods is becoming a tradition in institutions. It is known that the teaching of the lesson based on different methods ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.

In addition, to a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, ability to solve one's tasks without difficulty today to educate mature professionals with the ability. [2:238] Our pedagogic teachers use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies their use is the main factor of increasing the quality and efficiency of education they should understand that, and that this is what the times demand.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Each pedagogue in learning based on diagnosis of pedagogical innovations positive, developing situations as well as negative manifestations in his experience it should not be forgotten that it is necessary to take into account the existence A young pedagogue is at the educational institution for effective functioning of the positive and existing in his work experience negative aspects are required to be clearly demonstrated on the basis of diagnosis.[3:74] Diagnostic methods used to study innovative processes are as follows it is necessary to clearly convey to the minds of future teachers that it consists of

- Pedagogical needs, interests of future teachers, separately
- Systematic study of important directions, in which teachers

Identification of difficulties encountered in the activity and the possibilities of their elimination;

- Ideas that serve to satisfy their interests and needs search for concepts and advanced pedagogical practices and higher pedagogical education putting into practice;

CONCLUSION

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. Speech skills in trainings during the educational process adequate attention to formation and development of social flexibility should be given. In addition, the success of each lesson in education has many aspects it depends on the correct organization of training. The lesson belongs to the teacher and the student should be based on creative cooperation. Only then students can think independently they receive, their will is trained.

REFERENCES

1. Pat McCarthy (1992). Strengths and Limitations of Teaching Methods. RN, MSN, 1992.
2. J. Michael. Spector (2001). Competencies for Online Teaching. ERIC Digest. Dec. 2001.